

A STUDY ON THE ROLE OF HUMAN RESOURCE IN ACHIEVING WORK-LIFE BALANCE

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1. INTRODUCTION

The organizations need to frame HR policies for their employees to enhance their skills. So that they can do their job effectively and the workplace flexibility will help them to solve their problems. In difficult situation HR role is most important in employee's life. In general the

ABSTRACT

Aim of the study: This study help the human resource department to identify their role in work-life balance of employees.

Design/ Methodology: Linear regression analysis used for hypothesis testing and Chi-square test is used to analyse the planning of work and age of the respondents.

Findings: The finding of the study indicated that proper planning and work place flexibilities reduce the stress level and increase the work-life balance of the employees. Most of the companies are not giving importance for their employees work-life balance. But they allot more works without any remuneration. The companies need to give monetary and non- monetary benefits to motivate the employees.

Practical Implications: Every organizations need to conduct periodical training to improve the skills of their employees also the management need to motivate them to participate in the managerial activities. The organizations need to provide good working conditions to reduce the stress level and improve their work-life balance. The good working atmosphere motivate the employees to concentrate their job.

Originality/ Value: According to the review of literature the most of the studies are concentrated on work-life balance in different field. But no study has been conducted to the role of HR in work-life balance of employees.

Keywords: Work-Life Balance, organizations, HR, Role of HR

Paper type: Research Paper

dualearning families are working more hours. The organizationalwork-life balance policieshelp them for the proper functioning at their work place and their home also it will reduce the workplace conflict.Due to demand of personal life most of the people are entering in toworking contract so that theWLB is most importantin their life. Achieving of WLB is difficult in the employee’s life. Work-life integrationof the personal and work responsibilities is the popular concept in the midst of employees. The HR needs to give more importance of employee’s concerns to achieve WLB.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Work-Life Balance (WLB)

Work-life balance is an important and challenge of every organizations and their employees. This study gives the framework about the WLB in the current scenario. This study highlight the role of HR in achieving WLB as well as it highlight the impact of poor work-life balance. This study help the employees to assess issues help to overcome their problems. Through this study the HR can get the knowledge of the importance of work life balance. WLB is means the time spend for doing the job and the time spend for their personal work and the time spend with others those who are loving. Due to demand of work most of the time the employees are giving utmost attention to their work and less time to handle the other responsibilities. Most of the employees need to achieve balance between job and personal life. Due to work demand they are struggling with personal life and professional life.

The organizations need to demonstrate the WLB programs to improve the skills of the employees, it will reduce the absenteeism, improve the employee commitment and employee job satisfaction, retention, accident rates and increase the productivity. The WLB programmes reduce the stress level of the employees so that they can concentrate their personal life and the professional life.

2.1.1 Importance of WLB

The WLB will improve employee’s overall well-being such as mental and physical health. This study have been analysed long working hours create health issues like depression, diabetes, drinking, memory loss and other diseases. The association between employees and employers may increase the productivity. So that the employees are working more hours than their normal working hours. The long working hours affect the WLB of the employees.

2.1.2 The Role of Human Resource

The human resource department need to help the employee to sustain the WLB. The human resource department need to take more care about the employees to identify the problems of the employees and help them to find solution. The companies need to include WLB policies in the human resource department. The human resource policies may include such as

- ❖ Flexible working arrangements
- ❖ Conduct employee training programs
- ❖ Employees welfare schemes
- ❖ Employees participation in the management process

2.2 Related Literature

Ashwini and Anand (2014) suggested that employees spend most of the time in their work place so managements should adopt welfare measures to satisfy the employees and introduced strategies and policies like fair compensation, job satisfaction, safety and health, training and development, opportunity to develop skill and growth, social integration to develop the WLB.

Aziz Mensah and Nicholas Kofi Adjei (2020) stated that most of the employees failed to maintain work-life balance due to work pressure and working conditions. So the companies need to reduce the work pressure and arrange very good working atmosphere to reduce the pressure and improve their skills.

Higgins and Duxbury (2015) studied, most of the women employees are taking more care and they are willing to take responsibilities as compared with the men employees. Women are willing to report to the high levels as compared with the men employees. The women employees are involved in more non-work activities like domestic work. Moreover the women employees have less family support for their professional activities and other personal activities.

Khaled Mahmud and SharminIdrish (2011) investigated the impact of six human resource strategies on employee intention to leave in Bangladeshi banks, including realistic job information, job analysis, work-family balance, career development, salary, and supervisor assistance. Employee inclination to depart was positively connected with work-family balance.

LoanaLupu and Mayra Ruiz – Castro (2019) ascertained that the organizations need to implement effective strategies in the sustainable manner. These effective strategies will help the employees to reduce the stress even in the high pressure and they can concentrate their work and increase the awareness of the WLB.

Muthukumar M, Dr.P.Kannadas and R.Savitha (2014) examined that usually the employees are spending their time with their organization or at home. The productivity of the employee's not only depends on work but it is related to their personal life. The WLB necessitates to maintain the balance between professional life and personal activities. This will reduces reduce the stress level and improve the WLB as well as increase the productivity.

Rakesh S. Patil, VarshaPatil, and PratibhaWaje (2011) investigated human resource management difficulties and practises in the software industry and discovered that as the work environment changed, more and more organisations admitted that their key people were leaving them. A new work-life balance policies is needed to the employee not only to attract, motivate, and retain essential 'knowledge workers,' but also to reinvent careers so that people remain loyal to the company.

SatishPuranam (2016) examined that Organizations conduct ongoing training programmes to improve connectivity and reduce travel requirements of women and it will help to improve their work life balance.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

94 questionnaire has been used for this research to collect primary data. Secondary data has been collected by articles and Internet.

Hypothesis

- i. H1: There is a relationship between maintain proper job description and increase overall efficiency.
- ii. H2: There is a relationship between employee participation in management process increase the efficiency of employees.

4. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

4.1 Exploratory factor analysis

KMO and Bartlett test of Sphericity check the sample adequacy and it quantifies the inter-correlation between the variables.

Table 1: KMO and Bartlett's test

KMO Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.877
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	355.913
	df	15
	Sig.	.000

KMO and Bartlett's test used to measure sampling adequacy for the variables. KMO test value = 0.877.

Table 2: Communalities

Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
planning of the work	1.000	.699
providing flexible approach towards the work	1.000	.770
maintain proper job description	1.000	.801
empathetic towards the employees	1.000	.710
conduct employee training programme	1.000	.696
Employee participation in management process	1.000	.399
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

The communalities indicates how much one variable is accounted for by the underlying factors taken together.

Table 3: Total Variance Explained

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	4.074	67.905	67.905	4.074	67.905	67.905
2	.752	12.534	80.439			
3	.402	6.700	87.139			
4	.345	5.751	92.889			
5	.222	3.702	96.591			
6	.205	3.409	100.000			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.						

4.2 Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Figure1: Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Goodness of Fit Test for CFA

Table 4: GOODNESS OF FIT TEST FOR CFA

S.NO	Measure	Recommended value	Observed Values	Interpretation
1	CMIN/DF	Between 1 and 3	2.457	Excellent
2	CFI	>0.95	.963	Excellent
3	GFI	>0.90	.926	Excellent
4	NFI	>0.90	.940	Excellent
5	IFI	>0.90	.963	Excellent
6	TLI	>0.90	.938	Excellent

The model fitness CMIN/DF= 2.457, the discrepancy divided by degrees of freedom is $22.116 / 9 = 2.457$, CFI = .963, GFI = .926, NFI = .940, IFI = .963 and TLI = .938.

4.3 Reliability Statistics

The Cronbach's Alpha value of work-life balance is 0.897, which is more than 0.7. The WLB factors Cronbach's Alpha values are given below:

Table 5: Reliability of work-life balance

	Scale Mean	Scale Variance	Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha
Planning of work	10.54	18.939	.729	.878
Providing flexible approach towards the work	10.29	19.132	.808	.866
Maintain proper job description	10.49	19.070	.821	.864
Empathetic towards the employees	10.20	19.819	.764	.874
Conduct employee training programme	10.05	19.234	.750	.875
Employee participation in management process	9.86	20.099	.519	.915

4.4 Crosstab Analysis

Table 6: Crosstab Analysis

Crosstab								
			Age				Total	
			Less than 30 years	30-40 age group	41-50 age group	Above 50 age group		
planning of the work	Strongly dis-agree	Count	7	6	25	15	53	
		% within Age	30.4%	40.0%	65.8%	83.3%	56.4%	
	Dis-agree	Count	8	7	9	3	27	
		% within Age	34.8%	46.7%	23.7%	16.7%	28.7%	
	Neutral	Count	2	1	2	0	5	
		% within Age	8.7%	6.7%	5.3%	0.0%	5.3%	
	Agree	Count	3	0	0	0	3	
		% within Age	13.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%	3.2%	
	Strongly agree	Count	3	1	2	0	6	
		% within Age	13.0%	6.7%	5.3%	0.0%	6.4%	
	Total		Count	23	15	38	18	94
			% within Age	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%

Most of the employees belongs the age group 41- 50 are strongly disagree the statement planning of the work. It was ascertained from this study most of the organizations are not plan their properly.

4.5 Chi-Square Test

Table 7: Chi-Square Test

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	23.185 ^a	12	.026
Likelihood Ratio	24.228	12	.019
Linear-by-Linear Association	14.488	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	94		

Pearson Chi-square value = 23.185 and P value = 0.026. P value <0.05, hence null hypothesis rejected. It was conclude from this study there is an association between planning of the work and age of the respondents.

4.6 Linear Regression Analysis

Table: 8:Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.827 ^a	.683	.665	.588	1.909

a. Predictors: (Constant), planning of the work, Employee participation in management process, empathetic towards the employees, conduct employee training programme, maintain proper job description

b. Dependent Variable: Increase overall efficiency

It was found from the above table R-square=.683, adjusted R-square= .665 which implies the work life balance factors create 68.3% variance on the dependent factor increase overall efficiency the regression fit is verified by the following ANOVA table.

Table: 9: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	65.613	5	13.123	38.002	.000 ^b
	Residual	30.387	88	.345		
	Total	96.000	93			

a. Dependent Variable: Increase overall efficiency

b. Predictors: (Constant), planning of the work, Employee participation in management process, empathetic towards the employees, conduct employee training programme, maintain proper job description

From the above table, it is found that $F = 38.002$, $P = .000$ are statistically significant @5% therefore it can be found that there is a significant relationship between the factors such as planning of the work, Employee participation in management process, empathetic towards the employees, conduct employee training programme, maintain proper job description and increase the efficiency of employees. The individual influence of all the factors can be estimated in the following coefficient table.

4.7 Testing of Hypothesis

H1: There is a relationship between maintain proper job description and increase overall efficiency.

H2: There is a relationship between employee participation in management process increase the efficiency of employees.

Table: 10: Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.178	.163		1.096	.276
	Maintain proper job description	.346	.110	.345	3.144	.002
	empathetic towards the employees	.181	.096	.173	1.880	.063
	conduct employee training programme	-.026	.089	-.027	-.291	.771
	Employee participation in management process	.170	.060	.206	2.840	.006
	planning of the work	.267	.090	.296	2.981	.004

a. Dependent Variable: Increase overall efficiency

From the above table it can be ascertained that Maintain proper job description ($\beta=345$, $t=3.144$, $P=.002$), Employee participation in management process ($\beta=.206$, $t=2.840$, $P=.006$) and planning of the work ($\beta=.296$, $t=2.981$, $P=.004$) are statistically significant @5% level of significance. It was ascertained from this study there a significant relationship between the factors such as maintain proper job description, employee participation in management process, planning of the work and increase overall efficiency of the employees.

8. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- ❖ It was ascertained from this study proper planning will help the human resource to improve the skills.
- ❖ Provide flexible working will reduce the stress level and motivate the employees to concentrate their work.

- ❖ Every HR department need to maintain proper job description.
- ❖ The HR and management should have empathetic towards their employees at all levels.
- ❖ HR need to conduct periodical training to their employees.
- ❖ Human Resource department need to encourage their employees to participate in the management process.

9. CONCLUSION

WLB is one of the issue of many employees. The employees are the assets of every organization. The activities of HR department will affect the employee's performance. The lack of employee's skills will affect the organizations. The organizations need to implement good human resource policies to reduce the work load of the employees and improve the WLB. The good human resource policies help the employees make the employees happy and they can concentrate their work. Through the happiest employees the productivity of the organizations automatically increase. Thus, this research conclude human resource department make good policies with the help of management to attain the goal of the organizations.

10. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study is concentrated only the role of human resource and the sample size is only 94. This study is one of the review for future researchers. The researchers concentrated on work-life balance and their benefits of employees. The future researchers can do the research on work – life balance of police officers. No deep research has been conducted in this area.

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